

Effect of radiation on the pigment content, gas exchange parameters, and activity of nitrate reductase in cotton leaves

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The effect of different doses of radiation on the content of photosynthetic pigments, gas exchange parameters, and the activity of the enzyme nitrate reductase (NR) in leaves was studied during the ontogenesis of the cotton plant. The obtained results show that γ -rays have a retarding effect on the rate of photosynthesis and the amount of photosynthetic pigments in doses above 100 Gy, and a regulatory effect in doses of 5-50 Gy. It was found that at these doses, the rate of photosynthesis and the amount of pigments increase in the phase of true leaf formation (TLF), this increase continues weakly in the budding (BP) and flowering (FP) phases, and it gradually decreases in the seed ripening or boll opening phases (BOP). The amount of carotenoids, unlike chlorophylls, increases in all stages of plant ontogenesis at high radiation doses. All this indicates that γ -radiation has a stimulating effect on the activity of NR in the leaves of higher plants, leading to high yield.

Keywords: *Gossypium hirsutum* L., radiation, stress, Nitrate reductase, pigment, adaptation

INTRODUCTION

The more efficient absorption of mineral elements by the plant roots plays an important role in the regulation of the activity of the photosynthetic apparatus at the genetic level by increasing the productivity of higher plants. The decrease in the productivity of higher plants under the influence of abiotic stress factors shows that it is important to study the nature of photosynthetic variations.

It was found that ultraviolet rays (280-320 nm) cause serious changes in plant cells and then the mechanisms that weaken the effect of radiation are activated (Jafarov, 2014; Barnes et al., 2018). Maskernes, et al. detected two types of changes against the effect of radiation in the *Pisum sativum* plant: 1. changes in the content and structure of chloroplasts, 2. changes in the expression of genes encoding plastid proteins (Mackerness et al., 1998).

In order to reveal the tolerance mechanisms of living organisms against the effects of environmental factors, their responses to stress should be studied at the population-molecular hierarchical levels (Bais et al., 2018).

Treatment of seeds with γ -rays causes changes in plants at the genetic level, according to which breeding scientists can create salt-tolerant, quick-

growing, and productive genotypes (Ashraf et al., 2003).

Biochemical separation of all soluble proteins in plants shows that at 50 Gy irradiation dose, seedlings have more soluble proteins (21.03±1.82 mg/g FW), and at 10 Gy irradiation dose, this indicator is 14.49±4.04 mg /g FW (Ling et al., 2008).

It was found that after γ -irradiation of tomato plant cells, 15 and 17 kDa molecular weight protective proteins were synthesized in the cytoplasm and 22 kDa in the mitochondria (Banzet et al., 1998).

As the photosynthetic apparatus and its pigment systems weaken under the influence of radiation and salt stress, a number of changes occur in metabolism, as a result of which plant growth, development, photosynthesis, respiration, metabolism of proteins and amino acids, as well as the activity of many enzymes decrease (Akram and Ashraf, 2011).

Due to the effect of salt stress, the structure of chlorophyll and chlorophyll-lipid-protein complex is destroyed (Akca and Samsunlu, 2012). The amount of chlorophyll depends on the type of plant, nature, development phases, dose of radiation and concentration of salts. Salts have a more toxic effect on chlorophyll *a* than on chlorophyll *b*

(Stroganov et al., 1970).

As it is known, the growth and development of plants and their productivity are closely related to nitrogen exchange. From this point of view, the study of the activity of the NR enzyme localized in the leaves of higher plants under the influence of radiation is of great scientific and practical importance.

Taking these into account, the main goal of the work was to study the changes in the amount of photosynthetic pigments in cotton leaves under the influence of different doses of radiation, and the physiological-biochemical changes that occur as a result of the effect of these changes on NR activity, which is the main enzyme in nitrogen metabolism.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The variety Ganja 182 of the *Gossypium hirsutum* L. cotton genus was taken as the research object. The seeds were planted according to the following scheme:

- 1) Control plants - planting non-irradiated seeds,
- 2) Planting seeds treated with γ -rays at doses of 1, 5, 10, 50, 100, and 200 Gy.

Cotton seeds were germinated within 5-6 days under natural conditions. After the 1st leaf stage of sprout development (we consider this stage as zero-day or control), irrigation was continued until the end of vegetation in the I and II group samples shown in the scheme.

Treatment of seeds with γ -rays. Cotton seeds were irradiated with doses of 1, 5, 10, 50, 100, and 200 Gy using a Co60-irradiation source in the RUXUND-20000 device at the scientific experiment department "Isotopic Radiation Sources" of the Institute of Radiation Problems. The seeds were disinfected in a 0.3% H₂O₂ solution for 15 min, washed several times with distilled water, and placed in a thermostat for germination in Petri dishes. Received seedlings were watered periodically with ordinary tap water in the control variants, and in the trial variants, the seedlings were watered with salt solutions. The development of sprouts continued in chambers with a temperature of 25-28°C, a photoperiod of 14 hours, a relative humidity of 60-70%, and a light intensity of 15-20 lux.

Total amount of proteins was determined by the Lowry colorimetric method (Lowry et al., 1951).

The intensity of photosynthesis (P_n) and the rate of transpiration (T_r) were determined using an infrared gas analyzer LI COR-6400 XT Postable Photosynthesis System (Biosciences, USA).

Determination of the intensity of transpiration. The intensity of transpiration (T_r) was determined by the Ivanov method (Ivanov et al., 1950). To determine T_r, the leaves were weighed immediately after plucking and they were weighed again after 3-4 minutes of storage. In this case, it is necessary to determine the leaf area and the intensity of free evaporation. For this purpose, the examined leaf is placed on a square of the known area on graph paper, cut to the size of the square and weighed. The leaf area is calculated by the following formula:

$$a/b=c/s$$

where: *a* - square paper weight; *b* - the weight of the plant figure; *c* - area of the square; *s* - area of the leaf.

To determine T_r, the weight of a chemical beaker filled with water was determined at room temperature. After 30 minutes, the beaker was weighed again and the amount of evaporated water was measured. T_r (g/m² · h) was calculated by the following formula:

$$T_r = n \times 10000 \times 60 / (s \times t)$$

where: *n* - amount of water evaporated (g); *s* - leaf area (cm²); *t* - storage period (min); 10000 - conversion factor of cm² to m²; 60 - conversion factor of min to an hour.

NR activity assay. 100 mM Tris-HCl buffer (pH 7.5) containing 1 mM vinyl acetate (supplemented with 1 mM EDTA, 1 μM Na₂MoO₄, 5 μM flavin adenine dinucleotide (FAD), 3 mM dithiothreitol (DTT), 1 % BSA, 12 mM 2-mercaptoethanol, 250 μM PMSF, 2 ml) was added to 0.5 g of leaves and extracted with quartz sand in a mortar at +4°C. The obtained extract was precipitated at 5,000g for 10 minutes, then the precipitate was discarded, and work was continued with the supernatant. The reaction medium (0.5 ml) for NR activity: 0.12 ml 0.167 M phosphate buffer (pH 7.5); 0.04 ml of 0.1 M KNO₃; 0.02 ml of 2 mM FMN; 0.02 ml of Na₂SO₄, 8 mg/ml, of 0.095 M NaHCO₃; and 0.2 ml of the enzyme preparation.

The test tubes were shaken, then they were placed in a water bath at 25°C to initiate the reaction. A drop of paraffin oil was added to the test tubes to prevent oxidation of the reducing agent by air oxygen by forming a thin layer on the reaction medium. To stop the reaction after 30 min, the reaction mixture was shaken rapidly until all reducing agents were oxidized (as evidenced by a change in color from light yellow to yellow). The amount of nitrites formed as a result of the enzymatic reduction of nitrates was determined by adding 0.3 ml of 1% sulfonamide prepared from 3N HCl, followed by 0.3 ml of 0.02% N-(1-Naphthyl)ethylenediamine dihydrochloride solution. After the obtained mixture was

centrifuged at 5,000g for 15 minutes, its optical density was determined at a wavelength of 540 μm . The amount of nitrites was determined based on the standard deviation curve (Ferrari, Varner, 1969).

Determination of the amount of photosynthetic pigments. For this, the leaves were extracted in 96% ethyl alcohol and the absorbance of each pigment was measured in its absorption spectrum in an Ultraspec 3300pro (USA) spectrophotometer (Wettstein, 1957) and the amount of carotenoids was measured by the (Wintermans, De Mots, 1965) method.

$$\text{Chl a (mg/l)} = 12.7 \cdot \text{D663} - 2.69 \cdot \text{D645} \\ (\text{Wettstein, 1957})$$

$$\text{Chlb (mg/l)} = 22.9 \cdot \text{D645} - 4.68 \cdot \text{D663} \\ (\text{Wettstein, 1957})$$

$$\text{Chla+b (mg/l)} = 29.0 \cdot \text{D652}$$

$$\text{Car (mg/l)} = 4.695 \cdot \text{D440.5} - 0.268 \cdot (\text{Cl a+b mg/l}) \\ (\text{Wintermans and De Mots, 1965})$$

Statistical analysis. The values given in the table are mathematical averages and reflect the mean square deviation. Average mathematical errors and deviations ($M \pm m$) were taken into account during the analysis of the research results. Differences were considered significant when the accuracy probability was $R \leq 0.05$. The obtained results were processed using "Statistics for Windows 10.0" and "Microsoft Office Excel 2010" computer programs.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In the context of the adaptation of higher plants to the action of radiation and salts of various compositions, it is of great scientific and practical importance to study the effect of high salt concentrations and radiation doses on plant growth and development, biometric traits, and the enzyme systems of photosynthesis and respiration.

We conducted our experiments according to the scheme given in the chapter Materials and Methods, and the results are presented in the table. As seen in the table, the influence of different doses of radiation on the dynamics of changes in the amount of photosynthetic pigment systems, depending on the individual phases of the ontogenesis of the cotton plant, occurs on a different spectrum, and the amounts of photosynthetic pigments vary in a wide range. In the TLF phase of seedling development, radiation had a more toxic effect on the amount of pigments at doses higher than 100 Gy. In this period, the development of pigments in leaves was highly stimulated at a radiation dose of 5-50Gy. Changes in the amount of chlorophyll *a* due to the effect of radiation occurred similarly in the phases of

ontogenesis (Table 1).

The amount of chlorophyll *a*, chlorophyll *b* and their sum changed similarly under the effect of radiation. At low levels of radiation, amounts of photosynthetic pigments increased gradually during plant ontogenesis, including the flowering phase. At the dose level of 100 Gy, the amount of chlorophylls according to each phase decreased over time by ~80-85% compared to the previous development phases, and the decrease was more intensive at radiation doses above 200 Gy.

In the BOP phase of vegetation, the amount of chlorophyll *a* and *b* increased to a certain extent in the control and at low radiation doses of 5-10 Gy and decreased at higher doses (Table 1). The ratio of chlorophyll *a/b* was greater than one in all phases and radiation doses, which proves that the intensity of photosynthesis increased and the reaction center of PS II became more active under those experimental conditions.

Table 1. Dynamics of changes of some physiological-biochemical indicators in cotton leaves under the influence of radiation in different phases of ontogenesis

Ontogenesis C	Radiation, Qy					
	5	10	50	100	200	
Chlorophyll a						
TLF	0.65	0.71	0.83	0.74	0.49	0.19
BP	0.83	0.88	1.01	0.96	0.62	0.18
FP	0.87	0.90	1.71	1.28	0.66	0.09
BOP	0.88	0.96	1.23	1.13	0.36	0.04
Chlorophyll b						
TLF	0.31	0.44	0.58	0.5	0.28	0.09
BP	0.49	0.45	0.64	0.64	0.53	0.15
FP	0.52	0.51	0.96	0.73	0.69	0.06
BOP	0.54	0.76	0.88	0.79	0.31	0.04
Chlorophyll a+b						
TLF	0.96	1.15	1.41	1.24	0.77	0.28
BP	1.32	1.33	1.65	1.6	1.15	0.33
FP	1.39	1.41	2.67	2.01	1.35	0.15
BOP	1.42	1.72	2.11	1.92	0.67	0.08
Chlorophyll a/b						
TLF	2.09	1.61	1.43	1.48	1.75	2.11
BP	1.69	1.96	1.58	1.5	1.17	1.2
FP	1.67	1.76	1.78	1.75	1.25	1.5
BOP	1.63	1.26	1.39	1.43	1.16	1.0
Carotenoids						
TLF	1.28	1.5	1.62	1.68	1.44	1.3
BP	1.33	1.58	1.71	1.80	1.38	1.3
FP	1.46	1.65	1.84	1.97	1.51	1.46
BOP	1.58	1.7	1.91	2.1	1.93	1.85
Chlorophyll a+b/Carotenoid						
TLF	0.75	0.77	0.87	0.74	0.53	0.22
BP	0.99	0.84	0.96	0.89	0.85	0.25
FP	0.95	0.85	1.45	0.89	0.89	0.1
BOP	1.03	0.43	1.1	0.68	0.35	0.04

Note: TLF-true leaf formation phase, BP-phase of budding or formation of sympodial branches, FP-flowering phase, BOP-ripening (or boll opening phase) fazasi. Amount of pigments-mg/ml wet weight, C-control. The values given in the table are the mean of three replicates.

Unlike chlorophylls, the amount of carotenoids increased depending on the growth phases of the plant and radiation doses until the end of ontogenesis, which can be attributed to the protective function of carotenoids under severe stress conditions.

Based also on the results of our previous experiments, at optimal radiation doses (1-50 Gy), the changes in the biometric parameters of the plant, the amount of pigments in the leaves, and even P_n and T_r completely match each other.

As seen in Table 2, P_n decreased ~0.4 and ~0.6 fold in BP and FP compared to the control, respectively, and T_r changed according to P_n . The amount of carbon accumulated in the intercellular spaces (C_i) at the radiation dose of 50 Gy, which we consider the optimal dose limit, increased from the TLF phase of ontogenesis to BOP. Nevertheless, P_n and T_r increased up to the FP of plant development and decreased in the subsequent phases at unchanged radiation dose. Regardless of the cause, T_r and the amount of CO_2 diffusing from the atmosphere into the intercellular spaces through stomatal cells are also reduced in leaves. A decrease in the amount of CO_2 , one of the substrates of photosynthesis, in the intercellular spaces leads to a weakening of P_n and ultimately to a decrease in biological productivity (Table 2). As noted in the literature, the mesophyll conductance, g_s , has a superior role in the regulation of P_n (Siddique et., 1999).

The parallel study of the activity of nitrate reductase (NR), which has an important role in nitrogen metabolism, protein and amino acid metabolism, with pigment and gas parameters can contribute to clarifying the role of physiological processes in the creation of adaptive mechanisms in plants. For this purpose, the dynamics of changes in the NR activity in the leaf extracts of the plants exposed to various radiation doses were studied during the ontogenesis of the cotton plant. As seen in the table, we have discussed the results we obtained at the dose of 50 Gy, which we consider to be the optimal dose of radiation. We believe that this way of setting the issue is more appropriate and will allow us to get more correct results.

NR activity was found to increase during plant development including the flowering phase. In the later development periods of ontogenesis, the activity of the enzyme decreased and eventually reached its lowest value. During the FP, when NR activity was the highest, the amount of pigments, except for carotenoids, was also high. In BOP, the amount of C_i increased against the background of the weakening T_r and P_n (Table 2).

Table 2. Dynamics of changes of gas exchange parameters and NR activity in cotton leaves under the influence of 50 Gy radiation in different phases of ontogenesis

Ontogenesis	Radiaton, 50 Qy				Radiaton, 50 Qy			
	C_i	P_n	T_r	NR	C_i	P_n	T_r	NR
TLF	264	49.9	6.02	1.617	264	49.9	6.02	1.617
BP	282	49.8	6.14	1.652	282	49.8	6.14	1.652
FP	289	54.1	2.4	1.687	289	54.1	2.4	1.687
BOP	296	36.6	2.08	1.289	296	36.6	2.08	1.289

Note: P_n - photosynthesis intensity $-\mu\text{mol } CO_2 \text{ m}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$, T_r -transpiration intensity- $\text{mmol } CO_2 \text{ m}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$, C_i - CO_2 amount in the intercellular space- $\text{mmol } CO_2 \text{ m}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$. NR-nitrate reductase- $\text{mg } NO_2^- \text{ min}^{-1} \cdot \text{mg}^{-1} \text{ protein}$. The values given in the table are the mean of three replicates.

We can conclude that the combined function of photosynthetic pigments and gas exchange indicators, with the activity of the NR enzyme, maintains the intensity of photosynthesis at a high level, which is a global process, causing thereby the plant organism to tolerate the effects of stress for a certain period of time.

Thus, the synchronous change in the amount of chlorophylls and carotenoids, biometric indicators, the intensity of photosynthesis, amount of gas parameters and NR activity is a sign of adaptation in higher plants and serves for the creation of traits of high tolerance and avoidance of the effects of stress in plants.

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Radiasiyanın pambıq yarpaqlarında piqmentlərin, qaz parametrlərinin miqdarına və nitratreduktaza fermentinin fəallığına təsiri

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Məqalədə radiasiyanın müxtəlif dozalarının pambıq bitkisinin ontogenezində fotosintezin piqmentlərinin miqdarına, yarpaqlarda qaz mübadiləsi parametrlərinə, nitratreduktaza (NR) fermentinin fəallığına təsiri tədqiq edilmişdir. Alınan nəticələr göstərir ki, γ -şüalar 100 Qr-dən yuxarı dozalarda fotosintezin sürətinə, fotosintetik piqmentlərin miqdarına ləngidici, 5-50 Qr dozalarda isə tənzimləyici təsir edir. Müəyyən olunmuşdur ki, bu dozalarda cücərtinin əsl yarpaqların yaranması (ƏYF) fazasında fotosintezin sürəti və piqmentlərinin miqdarı artır, qönçələmə (QF) və çiçəkləmə fazalarında (ÇF) bu artım zəif davam edir, toxumların yetişməsi, yaxud qozaların açılması fazalarında (QAF) isə tədricən azalır. Karotinoidlərin miqdarı isə xlorofillərdən fərqli olaraq yüksək radiasiya dozalarında bitkinin ontogenezinin bütün mərhələlərində artır. Bütün bunlar onu göstərir ki, ali bitkilərin yarpaqlarında NR fermentinin fəallığına γ -radiasiya stimullaşdırıcı təsir göstərməklə yüksək məhsulun əmələ gəlməsinə səbəb olur.

Açar sözlər: *Gossypium hirsutum* L., radiasiya, stres, nitratreduktaza, piqment, adaptasiya